

**ACCURATE POSITIONING OF BRACES AS ONE OF THE
FUNDAMENTAL FACTORS OF SUCCESSFUL ORTHODONTIC
TREATMENT**

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Introduction: In modern orthodontics, there are currently two methods of fixing braces. Direct bonding, which is performed directly by an orthodontist in the clinic, and indirect fixation, which requires a preparatory stage in the laboratory (Proffit W.R., 2008; Persin L.S., 2015; Arsenina O.I., 2012; Ospanova G.B., 2017). There is a growing interest in indirect bonding to improve the accuracy of braces positioning (Bennett D.K., McLaughlin R.P., 2005). This method opens up opportunities for orthodontists, as it allows them to fix braces and orthodontic locks in the correct position. With direct bonding, this is not always possible and is often difficult due to insufficient fixation of the bracket system and difficulties in accessing the lateral teeth. Indirect bonding makes it easy to view all the planes of the tooth, which is difficult to achieve intraorally, without factors such as soft tissue or saliva. However, despite the many advantages, one of the disadvantages of indirect bonding is that the edges of the braces and locks change during sandblasting. This negatively affects the degree of fixation of the braces directly on the tooth. This was the reason for conducting this scientific study. The goal is to increase the effectiveness of orthodontic treatment by improving the positioning of the bracket system.

Materials and methods: On the basis of the Department of Pediatric Dentistry Samarkand State Medical University, a study was conducted on the location of braces after indirect fixation on plaster models made of various

materials. The bracket systems of the first group were fixed on plaster models using standard orthodontic adhesives using the traditional method of indirect fixation. Before fixing the braces directly to the teeth in the oral cavity, the adhesive residues were removed by sandblasting. The second group of braces was fixed on plaster models using caramelized sugar. Using a heated electric spatula, a drop of caramel sugar was applied to the plaster model and to the bracket pad and pressed into the plaster in the right place. Then the mouthguards were made according to standard methods, and the places where the braces were installed were treated with a soft brush under a stream of warm water. Results and discussion

Microscopic examination of the braces installation sites revealed clear differences between the initial surface of the braces installation sites and their condition after fixation with orthodontic glue and caramelized sugar. However, after using caramelized sugar, there were no differences from the initial state of the bracket system. After fixing the orthodontic adhesive on the area of the bracket system, sandblasting should be carried out for removal.¹² The II International Scientific and Practical Conference "Modern Pediatric Dentistry" and the II International Scientific and Practical Conference "Modern Pediatric Dentistry and Orthodontics" Young Scientist's Day, changes were observed on the surface of the bracket base. Adhesive residues were observed on the surface of the bracket, which affected the positioning accuracy. Excess material on the brace pad can lead to unwanted tooth movement such as rotation and torque changes. There was also a smoothing of retention points at the place of the bracket installation, and the accumulation of abrasive powder particles at these points can weaken the adhesion between the bracket and the tooth, which can subsequently lead to peeling of the bracket from the tooth surface. To solve this problem, we suggest using caramelized sugar as an adhesive on plaster models.

Conclusion. Thus, this study has shown that the indirect bonding method using caramelized sugar is recommended to improve the positioning accuracy of the bracket system. This eliminates errors in controlling the fit of the bracket base,

thereby increasing the fixation of the bracket to the teeth and eliminating positioning inaccuracies, which leads to shorter treatment time and more stable functional and aesthetic results.

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